
**JUNGLE JUSTICE AND GOVERNANCE IN AKWA IBOM STATE,
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Jungle justice has always been an alarming social problem in Nigeria; and despite the many interventions by the criminal justice system, the rate of occurrences across the country is arguably still high. This paper examines the historical origin of jungle justice and governance in Nigeria and various measures taken by the government and community leaders to discourage this illegal practice. The study applied the Retributive Theory of Justice in order to explain the concept, while desk-based library research blended with some degree of observations, was adopted as the method of research. We utilized data from secondary source, case studies, extant literature as well as conceptual, theoretical and empirical studies reviewed from other studies for conclusion and recommendations. Findings from the study have shown that majority of the victims of jungle justice are innocent while some are mistaken identities and are persecuted due to mob constraints which do not allow them to defend themselves. The study recommends (amongst others) that the Nigerian Police Force should establish a police-community trust relationship

for crime prevention and control; the police presence should be drawn closer to the grassroots through the creation of security patrol personnel.

Keywords: Jungle Justice, Human Rights, Governance, Crime

Introduction

Many indigenous ethnic groups like the Hausa/Fulani, Igbo and Yoruba had existed before the advent of colonialism and they had their traditional measures of social control and governance until they were later amalgamated into one geographical boundary known as Nigeria in 1914. The act of jungle justice predates colonialism. In the pre-colonial era, people who were caught on theft were buried alive in the evil forest while others were tightened to a tree to be eaten up by wild animals. In riverine areas, those who were caught stealing were tightened to a sand bag on their back and beaten, then finally thrown into the river. All these were done without any judicial process of trial. These measures served as deterrence in order to reduce the menace of theft and other criminal acts in the society before the English law was introduced in colonial era. Subsequently, every existing State in the world today has an established government vested with the rights and responsibility to protect lives and property of her citizens. The government now oversees governance and maintains law and orderliness in the society. Scholars have argued that handling these sacred responsibilities to the State and her machinery is to avoid a situation where the State would be driven into anarchy, chaos, aggression, insurgence, and conflicts (Adu-Gyamfi, 2014).

Jungle justice, also known as mob justice, is a form of public extrajudicial killing where an alleged criminal is humiliated, beaten and in some cases, set ablaze by an angry mob (Ubabukoh, 2013). It is often said that two wrongs do not make a right and this is a situation to the scenario of jungle justice that has become a living normal in Nigeria most especially, in cities like Uyo, Aba, Calabar, Imo, Kaduna, Kano, Rivers, Delta among others (Orabueze, Okoye and Ohaeto, 2013). It has been researched that the main reason people resort to jungle justice is because of lack of trust in the criminal justice system and the injustice played by the judicial system where criminals are favoured as far as they are close to the ruling elites in the society. Thus, the system of government in a nation is to restore law and order into the state of chaos and anarchy where only the strong survives (Orabueze, Okoye and Ohaeto, 2013). Therefore, the state in carrying out its functions established laws that would help in monitoring and guiding the conducts of both the ruled and the ruler. In this regard, the government of any given society as entrenched in the constitution

(which may either be written or unwritten), is principally charged with the responsibility of maintaining law and order in the State. Through the provisions of the constitution which is the supreme law of any modern State, a State may proceed to make other subsidiary laws which would be applied in maintaining peace, order and stability (Okorie, 2023).

Peter (2014) and Amara (2015) independently observed that jungle justice has become a form of public extra-judicial killing in Nigeria, where an alleged criminal is beaten, humiliated or summarily executed by an angry crowd. This practice of jungle justice continues to attract a lot of attention globally, most especially in Nigeria because of high crime rate. This, therefore, means that Nigeria Police Force and other law enforcement agencies saddled with the responsibility of protection of lives and properties have arguably failed in their primary responsibilities, resulting in a lack of public trust in the Nigerian judicial system, thereby, forcing the neighbourhoods in towns and cities to resort to jungle justice at any slightest provocation.

Also, scholars have opined that the police in Nigeria are corrupt and even when criminals are caught and handed over to them, they are often not charged to court after money might have exchanged hands (Ubabukoh, 2013). However, the situation has increased the desperation and frustration in many people, hence, they resort to jungle justice, which has become the only way many people feel justified in expressing their dissatisfaction over a failing criminal justice system (Onuoha, 2010; Inyang and Abraham, 2013). It is against this backdrop, therefore, that this paper examines why people take the law into their hands by engaging in jungle justice with specific focus in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The menace of jungle justice can be considered as one of the highest forms of murder and extra-judicial killing that has taken over the streets of many cities in Nigeria. One certain thing is that jungle justice, irrespective of the justification people may tend to give to it, is an inhumane act and is considered as a generational crime against humanity. Contemporarily, it is a common way of thought among members of the low class of individuals in society who believe the police and the court proceedings delay and may possibly lead to denial in the administration of justice. This compels the people to resort to jungle justice by killing an accused who has not been proven guilty by a court (Jeju, 2012).

According to Sanni (2017), it seems as if the structures as laid up by the alien laws have not been satisfying to the members of the community that they resort to taking the laws into their hands by way of jungle justice. From various observations made in studies, it appears that this social problem of jungle justice is on the increase as the year goes by. There are multiple incidents of jungle justice which have made the Nigerian people and government to appear so irresponsible, bloody, inhumane, and savagery in the international comity of nations.

The study agrees that a person, who is accused of committing a crime ought to be charged accordingly and if found wanting, he or she is to be punished in accordance with the law. It is therefore not in the hands and purview of the public to angrily use the alleged person as a burnt offering. The disturbing question remains: why should people take law into their hands? To answer this, the following questions should be considered:

- i. Could it be because of lack of confidence on the criminal justice system?
- ii. Could it be because of fear of retaliation by the accused person?
- iii. Could it be because of informal settlement by the family/community?
- iv. Could it be because of jungle justice would serve as deterrent?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the origin of jungle justices in Nigeria, while the specific objectives were:

- i. To investigate the factors that cause jungle justice in Nigeria;
- ii. To make recommendations that would help in the reduction of the menace of jungle justice in Uyo, South-south Nigeria.

Literature Review

In pre-colonial Africa, society was governed using traditional measures to ensure stability of law and order. People who acted contrary to societal norms and values were subjected to flogging, payment of fine, banishment amongst others. People who were caught culpable for theft were subjected to public disgrace; they were beaten and paraded naked, some were painted with charcoal from head to toe, and others were buried alive in the evil forest while others were bound to a tree to be eaten up by wild animals. For residents in riverine communities, alleged criminals were usually bonded to a sandbag and thrown into the sea to die even without judicial trial. These measures were to serve as deterrence in order to reduce crime in our traditional society.

The doctrine of Audi Partem Alteram emphasizes that both parties should be heard for it to be deemed that justice has been served. So the general law is that when a person is accused of any crime, the person is assumed to be innocent until the person has been proven guilty in a competent court of law; and the person cannot be deemed to have been proven guilty in appropriate order unless the person is allowed to state his side of the case and view of events as they occur. The law offers a certain level of protection to an accused person such as defenses, exceptions, provisions among others, which may be an avenue where a person who would have been guilty would be freed by the law (Abati, 2002).

Opinions suggest that there exist unquestionable character amongst officers of the Nigeria Police Force and it had gotten to the extent where the police would distort files and purposely misfire in some cases because they have already settled out of court (Ubabukoh, 2013). It is also arguable that corruption has eaten deep into the fabrics of the judiciary, therefore, the court no longer base her decision on the evidence adduced before it but on their interests which have been induced. It is also obvious that the snail or millipede movement of courtroom adjudication and litigation of criminal matters has made people to lose faith in the court system which ideally should be the last hope of the common man. These exacerbate the rising cases of jungle justice.

Conceptual Clarification

Jungle Justice: According to Luke (2013), jungle justice refers to the situation where a person who is alleged to have committed a crime is being punished by the people in accordance to no legal backing other than the justification of the mob. Crime (2016) observed that jungle justice is a complete violation of the fundamental human rights which are primarily available to individuals irrespective of the alleged offence, which criminalizes the actor by meting series of ill acts like stripping the accused naked, torturing the accused, setting the accused ablaze or butchering the accused into pieces. On his part, Abati (2015) argues that jungle justice is a situation where a group of lawless or non-law set of persons give unto themselves, the power of being in charge of punishing alleged criminals through ill-fated extra-judicial killing, horrendous beating or public humiliation and not taking into cognizance the rule of law and the fundamental rights of the alleged offence.

Human rights: These are categories of rights that a person is supposed to enjoy for being a citizen under the state. It is a kind of right, which helps a citizen to ascertain his fundamental rights. These rights are guided and protected by the state (UNDP, 1999).

Governance: Governance refers to the act of exercising political and legislative authority within the state.

Crime: Crime, in its most sense denotes those behaviours that are formally prohibited and punishable under criminal law. Such offences provide the subject matter of mainstream criminological investigation. Miller (1996) contends that the crime is the commission or omission of act which the law forbids or commands under pain of punishment to be imposed by the state.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopts the Retributive Theory of Justice propounded by Cesare Beccaria in 1764 and expanded by other scholars. For proper understanding of jungle justice in Nigeria, Retributive Theory of Justice is understood as a form of justice committed on the following three principles:

- i. That those who commit certain kinds of wrongful acts, paradigmatically serious crimes, morally deserve to suffer a proportionate punishment;
- ii. That it is intrinsically morally good without reference to any other goods that might arise if some legitimate punisher gives them the punishment they deserve;
- iii. That it is morally impermissible to intentionally punish the innocent or to inflict disproportionately large punishment on wrongdoers (Walen, 2016). The ‘just deserts’ theory of sentencing advocates that punishment should be proportionate to the gravity of the crime committed. Proponents of the just deserts philosophy emphasize the importance of due process, determinate sentences, and the removal of judicial discretion in sentencing practice.

Hirsch (1976) argues that “a just desert is a retributive theory of punishment”. Unlike theories that are primarily concerned with preventing future offenses, such as deterrence, rehabilitation and incapacitation, Contributivist Theories are only concerned with punishing crimes that have already been committed. The concept of “just deserts” seeks to preserve human dignity through punishment. It asserts that a person is a rational individual with the freewill to make a moral choice whether or not to engage in conduct known to be prohibited. Retribution under a just deserts principle treats a defendant as a dignified human being by responding to his or her conduct in a way that respects his or her choice to engage in wrongful behaviour (Hirsch, 1976).

Under this definition of retribution, crime is a conduct that disturbs the “right” relationships with the society. That is, the relationships between offender and victim, offender and community and victim and community. A criminal “deserves” to be punished because he or she has violated the “moral order”, and proportionality is the rope used to measure the type of punishment he or she deserves. In other words, the level of punishment must be proportional to the seriousness of the crime. Based on the law of retaliation, the punishment to be offered to an offender must be directly proportionate to the crime he or she has committed rather than taking laws for granted. Because punishment has been observed not to be commensurate to the crime committed, higher punishment might infringe upon the right of the alleged criminal but not jungle justice, as it contradicts the law of the federal republic of Nigeria.

Findings

Findings have shown that the majority of victims of jungle justice are innocent; some are mistaken identity. And this is because opportunities are usually not given to them to defend themselves, they become victim of circumstances. Over the years, some cities in Nigeria have experienced a high rate of this inhumane sub-culture of jungle justice where angry mobs for mere waiting or shouts of allegation, would chase and pin down the accused person and dish out all forms of battery on the person and usually end up setting the person ablaze. For whatever reasons this is done, it is a clear manifestation of human rights violations which must be curbed and addressed as soon as possible. The effect of these actions on the society is that it increases the number of hard hearted persons in the society, people whose morality does not prick them for taking another person’s life. Most of these victims if opportunities were given to them would have become reformed members of the society and contribute meaningfully to the growth and wellbeing of society. The people who are mobbed and killed without hearing could be innocent; the family of the person might have possibly lost a breadwinner, a father, husband, brother, son, mother, sister, aunt, daughter, wife amongst others.

Conclusion

The occurrence of jungle justice is to serve as deterrence to those engaging in theft in our society. But it is very unfortunate that even as the ill practice of jungle justice increases, it has not reduced crime rate in our society. This paper advocates that individuals and groups should say no to jungle justice because it has claimed many innocent lives through mistaken identity. This menace of indiscriminate killing of innocent people alleged to a crime should be discouraged in our society. While the world is making serious efforts to

eradicate the death penalty for capital offences, jungle justice is casting its anchor on the death penalty even on very minor offences. Where is our human conscience when a 23 year old boy is molested, beaten and burnt for stealing a cell phone?

Recommendations

1. Government should revoke the license of any traditional ruler where incidence of jungle justice takes place in his area of jurisdiction.
2. Government should punish all those involved in jungle justice to serve as deterrent to others
3. Government should reward individuals that give out information about perpetrators of jungle justice.
4. The judicial system should be more responsive to crime when they are called upon in order to avoid citizens engaging in jungle justice.
5. There is need for advocacy of human rights to the citizenry in order to sensitize them that jungle justice violates a person's rights to fair trial.
6. The Nigeria Police Force should establish a police community trust relationship in their statutory roles of crime prevention and control in our country.

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Appendix

Figure 1: Two boys from Ika L.G.A., were burnt in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State in 2021.

Source: Field Survey 2023

Figure 2: Three boys from Uyo were roasted alive in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State in 2022.

Source: Field Survey 2023

Figure 3: Two young men were lynched in Aba, Abia State.

Source: Field Survey 2023

Figure 4: Two thieves killed and beheaded, Enugu State.
Source: Field Survey 2023

Figure 5: Three thieves killed in Delta.
Source: Field Survey 2023

Figure 6: A young man identified as Eyo, aged 22, was set ablaze in Esu Street, off Edim Otop Street, Atimbo, Calabar municipality L.G.A. of Cross River State, March 2023.
Source: Field Survey 2023